

Concise Consumer Communication through Robust Labels for Bio-based Systems

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BBP	Bio-Based Product
CAWI	Computer Assisted Web Interviewing
FGD	Focus Group Discussions
D	Deliverable
ECS	Elastic Container Service
JWB	JSON Web Token
RDS	Relational Database Web Services
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
UI	User Interface

Executive Summary

This report presents the culmination of efforts undertaken in Task 2.4 (within WP2) of the 3-CO project, focusing on development of a digital solution prototype that integrate sustainability information effectively using advanced technologies like AI and gamification. The solution aim to enhance user experience and motivate sustainable consumer behaviour, addressing gaps in current digital solutions. The task was geared towards creating a mobile application that empower consumers to make environmentally conscious choices by providing them with comprehensive, easy-to-access information about bio-based products.

The task began a comprehensive analysis of existing digital solutions relevant to 3-CO project. we conducted extensive desktop research and engaged in interviews with solution providers to explore tools that assist consumers in making informed choices about biobased and eco-friendly products. Between April and June 2024, we interviewed several initiatives, revealing a landscape of digital solutions that originated from grassroots frustrations and minimal financial resources, highlighting the challenges of sustainability beyond initial funding. Also, online questionnaires and co-creation workshops were conducted to better understand the needs and challenges of consumers and involve them in development of potential solutions. As a result of these activities, three digital solution mock-ups were developed.

Afterwards, these mock-ups underwent rigorous consumer evaluation through structured focus groups and surveys across 10 countries. The feedback received was instrumental in choosing the right mock-up for further development, with a particular focus on usability, design clarity, and the relevance of features offered. A total of 28 specific requirements were identified and assessed in terms of their importance, difficulty level, and implementation priority. This structured assessment allowed the project team to strategically focus development efforts on features that provide the most significant impact on enhancing sustainable consumer behaviour.

The preferred app solution, as chosen by the majority of participants, incorporates features that support not only individual consumer needs, but also align with broader environmental goals. These include advanced functionalities like up to date sustainability assessments of Label and Certification Schemes (LCS), offline label search, a marketplace for uploading and reviewing bio-products, and knowledge sources about bioeconomy.

We faced multiple challenges during the development of the application as well as training the AI algorithm. We couldn't find a free database of ecolabels and had to build our own database to be incorporated to the app to give it offline functionality. We also needed lots of images to train the AI algorithm to identify the labels. Partners supported us in collecting images for the targeted labels and our technical team used data augmentation techniques (e.g., rotations, scaling, flipping, cropping, and changes in brightness or contrast) to optimize the performance of the algorithm despite this limitation.

Despite all the challenges, we were able to execute Task 2.4 successfully. The continued development and refinement of the solution, guided by consumer feedback and technological advancements, will be crucial in realizing the vision of a more informed and environmentally responsible society.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of 3-CO

The main goal of the 3-CO project is to develop and demonstrate the viability of a supportive framework for Label and Certification Schemes (LCS) on Business-to-Consumers (B2C) communication for industrial bio-based products (BBPs) that enables and supports consumers to make more sustainable purchasing choices. The focus of 3-CO is on consumer-oriented labelling options for industrial BBPs that are sustainable and circular in terms of resources, processes and materials used in their entire lifecycle. The supportive framework will consist of actionable guidelines for LCS owners that reflect consumers' and other stakeholders' needs, digital solutions to support better-informed decision-making processes of consumers, and policy recommendations on deploying social measures. The project aims to improve bio-based systems' sustainability performance and competitiveness, focusing on ten bio-based value chains (Table 1).

Table 1: 3-CO bio-based product value chains

#	3-CO product value chains
1	Baby clothing
2	T-Shirts
3	Shampoo
4	Wooden houses (Cross Laminated Timber or wooden frame houses)
5	Furniture
6	Cosmetics (make-up, etc.)
7	Biodegradable plant pots
8	Bio-based plastic toys
9	Bio-based PET/PEF bottles
10	Mattresses

These ten selected value chains are the focus of several 3-CO activities, also in Work Package 2, which will be described next.

1.2 Overview of WP2 Tasks and their relationship with T2.4

WP2 centres on consumer behaviour and sustainable decision-making, structured through a series of interrelated tasks:

Task 2.1 initiates the sequence by examining consumer attitudes towards sustainable products to understand the challenges and factors that influence purchasing decisions. This task provides foundational knowledge that feeds into the subsequent tasks by identifying key areas for intervention.

Task 2.2 evaluates best practices in sustainability communication, essential for developing effective communication strategies that Task 2.4 will later utilize.

Task 2.3 further explores consumer views through quantitative studies and qualitative research, offering direct insights that shape the smart solutions developed in Task 2.4. It assesses consumer responses to labeling systems and sustainable choices, directly informing the innovations in Task 2.4.

Task 2.4 itself focuses on the design and development of smart digital solutions that support sustainable decision-making of consumers. Building on the insights from Tasks 2.1 and 2.3, it develops prototypes that integrate sustainability information effectively using advanced technologies like AI and gamification. These solutions aim to enhance user experience and motivate sustainable consumer behaviour, addressing gaps in current digital supports. The task's outputs are crucial as they are evaluated by consumers, providing feedback that refines these technologies.

Finally, Task 2.5 integrates the insights and tools developed into a broader consumer-driven framework for label communication systems, ensuring that the digital solutions are aligned with consumer preferences and effective in promoting sustainable behaviours. Task 2.4 is central in transforming research insights into practical tools that facilitate more informed and sustainable consumer choices.

1.3 Scope of the report

This report focuses on the benchmarking and investigating existing digital tools and solutions, development and evaluation of smart digital solutions designed to support sustainable purchasing decisions. The scope of the report covers the entire process from ideation to prototype development, including the collection and assessment of inspirational examples, the design of AI-driven digital tools, and the integration of gamification elements to enhance user engagement. It details the methodologies used in developing these tools, the criteria for their effectiveness, and the results from consumer evaluations conducted across 10 EU countries (Poland, Finland, the Netherlands, Spain, Germany, Belgium, the United Kingdom, Italy, France, and Denmark). The report aims to offer valuable insights on the whole process undertaken in T2.4.

2 Methodology

The methodology employed in Task 2.4 for developing smart digital solutions to support sustainable purchasing decisions involves a structured, consumer-informed process that incorporates desktop research, interviews, and direct input from end-users:

1. Collection of Inspirational Examples: The development starts by examining existing digital solutions that facilitate sustainable decision-making across various sectors. This phase involves identifying successful applications and interviewing their developers to understand success drivers and uptake factors.

2. Analysis of existing tools: Insights from the inspirational examples lead to a comprehensive analysis, identifying where current digital solutions fall short and pinpointing specific consumer needs that new tools should address (can be found in Annex).

3. Consumer Surveys: After the analysis, a survey with a sample size of 3,000 respondents (300 participants from 10 target countries) was conducted to gather detailed information about consumer preferences, needs, and requirements. This step was crucial for tailoring the digital solutions to actual user expectations and enhancing the relevance of the developed tools.

4. Co-Creation Workshops: As part of Task 2.3, co-creation workshops were held with 40 participants, where they actively participated in ideating potential digital solutions. The results from these workshops and focus groups indicated a strong preference for app-based solutions, steering the development focus towards mobile platforms.

5. Mock-up Development and Feedback Collection: The development process transitioned into creating three unique UI design concepts in Figma, each focusing on different usability and aesthetic aspects. A questionnaire was designed and distributed as part of Task 2.3 to evaluate these mock-ups and collect consumer feedback. The insights gained from this feedback were instrumental in selecting the most effective design for further development.

6. Iterative Design and Development: The development process began with the creation of wireframes and mock-ups, refining user flows and layout concepts before any coding started. This design-driven approach provided a clear visual roadmap and helped streamline the development process. Continuous feedback was sought from partners and stakeholders, ensuring that the user interface designs and functionalities aligned with their expectations and the broader project goals. Functionality is introduced incrementally, allowing for regular testing and early identification of issues, which reduces risks and facilitated smooth development transitions. The iterative cycles are guided by a strong user-centered focus, prioritizing the end-user experience and incorporating feedback at every stage to refine and improve the solutions.

This comprehensive methodology, combining insights from initial research, direct consumer input through co-creation, and iterative design and testing, ensures that the final digital solutions are not only

technically sound but also highly aligned with consumer needs and preferences. This balanced approach enhances the likelihood of successful adoption and effectiveness of the digital tools in promoting sustainable purchasing decisions.

3 Examining existing digital solutions

We began this task with comprehensive desktop research to explore existing digital solutions that could assist consumers in making informed decisions about biobased and eco-friendly products. The table presented below categorizes a selection of companies under the 10 product categories identified in the 3-CO project. Our aim was to assess whether there are available apps platforms or website extensions capable of analyzing product labels and categorizing items according to their biobased or eco-friendly credentials. Additionally, we sought to understand the scope of these solutions, the specific product categories they cover, their effectiveness, user interface design, revenue models, and user reviews. For a detailed analysis of these digital solutions, please refer to Annex 1 of this report.

Table 2 list of existing digital solutions for each product category selected in 3-CO

App/ Website Extension	Type	Key features	Review
Think Dirty	App	Scan barcode to see potential health hazards and environmental impacts. Suggests safer and more eco-friendly alternatives.	Think Dirty has a user-friendly app but struggles with product identification. Users must pay for detailed information, and there's room for improvement in information transparency compared to other industry apps.
EWG Healthy Living	App	Provides information on ingredients in personal care and cleaning products, as well as food and water. Rates products on a scale from A to F.	The website and mobile app have user-friendly interfaces with a search bar and barcode scanner for easy product retrieval. They provide valuable safety information, but the app is not available for download in Spain.
Boycott	App/ Ext.	Identify companies behind products to see if their values align with yours. Scan barcodes or search for products.	The website lacks sustainability details and doesn't categorize products as bio or non-bio, offering only general product descriptions. Users appreciate the app for providing transparency about the companies and causes they support. Despite occasional issues, the overall reception of the app is positive.

Giki (Impact Score)	App	Scan barcodes to see impact on environment, society, and health. Suggests more sustainable and ethical alternatives.	Customers appreciate the app's openness, details on items they've bought, and emphasis on social responsibility and sustainability. Although sporadic problems like sluggish loading times or scant product information have been reported by a few, overall, the app is well received.
Skin Deep	Website	Provides information on ingredients in personal care products. Rates potential health hazards on a scale from 1 to 10.	Skin Deep functions as the personal database for EWG's Healthy Living, integrated with various resources for the development of their mobile application.
Yuka	App	Yuka deciphers product labels and analyses the health impact of food products and cosmetics.	Yuka is a quick and helpful app for assessing a product's health status, though it lacks in-depth research data. It's useful for consumers seeking quick tips while grocery shopping. The app appears transparent and unbiased, instilling confidence in users. Additional features are unlocked with a subscription to a paid plan.
INCI Beauty	App/ Website	INCI Beauty is a website and mobile application that provides consumers with information on the ingredients used in cosmetic and personal care products.	The application and webpage stand out in our CA study, being well-designed, interactive, and easy to use. They offer thorough information, and the premium plan's Offline feature distinguishes it from competitors. While extra features may not be necessary, occasional advertising banners are a minor annoyance, but not overly noticeable.

<p>Greenity</p>	<p>App</p>	<p>Allows you to search for various cosmetics by name or by scanning the barcode. All the ingredients of which that particular product is composed will then appear, classified with a colour scale ranging from green (excellent ingredient) to red (harmful ingredient).</p>	<p>The app's main drawback is its Italian-only language support. Despite a well-executed design and comprehensive INCI integration for cosmetic ingredient information, it lacks comprehensive product evaluations, relies on user reviews, has limited advertising, lacks information on product certification, and features a relatively small product database.</p>
<p>Junker</p>	<p>App</p>	<p>Junker identifies products through barcodes or manual input. Key features include easy waste categorization based on local collection methods and identification of labels by their shape along with some quizzes and guides for recycling.</p>	<p>Junker has a good intention, but its execution falls short, appearing abandoned with non-functional features and no updates for over four months. The label database is limited, lacking many descriptions. A positive aspect is the unique manual label search based on shape, but the maps option for recycling point locations is not optimized and shows no locations.</p>
<p>OneLabel</p>	<p>App</p>	<p>OneLabel provides individualised health insights, scans barcodes on food and cosmetics, and evaluates nutrition. It provides tools that enable users to make knowledgeable food decisions, such as goal-setting and community involvement.</p>	<p>OneLabel has a 7-day free trial, but upfront payment is required, which may deter some users. The app is exclusive to iOS, and associating a bank card upfront could be a turnoff for some. Despite these drawbacks, it offers a vast product database, quick barcode scanning, and easily navigable health courses. The app's search filtering enhances manual product searches.</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">Label Bio Hero (AllThings.Bio)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">App</p>	<p>Label Bio Hero, the companion app to AllThings.Bio (ATB), is a lifestyle app with a unique label scanner. Users can capture real-world labels for instant information from the app's EU bio-based product database, enhancing their understanding of bio-based alternatives</p>	<p>Label Bio Hero, with positive intentions, has room for improvement. The barcode scanner occasionally faces detection issues, and the database could be more extensive. Redirecting users to download a separate app for gaming may impact the user experience. Limited search filtering and a lack of updates for four months are areas that need attention. Addressing these points strategically will enhance user satisfaction and overall app performance.</p>
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In conclusion, after thorough analysis and comparison of various digital solutions aimed at assisting consumers in making informed decisions about biobased and eco-friendly products, INCI Beauty and Skin Deep have emerged as particularly noteworthy. INCI Beauty stands out for its comprehensive coverage both on its web platform and mobile application. The mobile app is especially user-friendly, offering barcode scanning capabilities and the option for offline usage through its paid annual plan—features that set it apart from its competitors. On the other hand, Skin Deep provides an exceptionally complete database on its web version, reducing the need for a mobile application. While its associated mobile app, EWG Healthy Living, is competently executed, it does lack certain functionalities like the listing of product certificates. However, Skin Deep compensates for these shortcomings with its own 'EWG VERIFIED' mark, which assures users of a product's transparency and adherence to health standards. These tools exemplify effective approaches to promoting sustainable consumer behaviors by providing detailed product insights and trustworthy certifications.

4 Interview with digital solution providers

Five main categories of digital solutions related to label scanning and biobased label databases were identified (detailed in table 3) . In Q2 2024, a dozen or so of providers corresponding to each category were contacted and requested to participate in an interview. (Only) a handful initiatives replied positively, also after sending several reminders. Interviews were held in the months April – June 2024. The main findings are presented below.

Which initiatives were interviewed?

A: **NABU Siegel-Check** is a free app developed by Naturschutzbund Deutschland for Android users. It helps users shop ecologically by identifying environmentally friendly products through scanning product logos. The scope is limited to food products; it will not be expanded to include additional products¹.

B: The **Label BioHero** app is designed to help people live more sustainably. The app can scan (eco-) logos, labels and EU certification schemes and then provides information. It focuses on non-food, non-energy bio-based products, such as packaging made from bio-based plastics and textiles made from organic cotton.

C: The **Junker** app is a mobile app from Italy that helps citizens to recycle products in a new, quick and easy way. Scanning a product's barcode, Junker identifies the product, breaks it down into components, and indicates how to sort them for recycling in the local area.

D: The Swiss-based **Labelinfo** label guide informs users about the scope of various ecolabels, creating transparency for consumers and supporting them in making sustainable consumption decisions. Only labels that appear on the Swiss market are covered. Currently food products and textiles are included

E: The Global Sustainable Enterprise Standard (**GSES**) holistically measures all facets of sustainability at the organization level and at product/process level. GSES aligns over 550 ecolabels and sustainable certificates and uses worldwide. It uses standards, auditing & certification tools and metadata to produce ratings (scores), published in the GSES database.

Table 3 Types of digital solutions considered for interview

#	Type of DS	Name of DS	URL
A	Label scanner app	NABU Siegel Check	https://siegelcheck.nabu.de/
B	Label scanner app	Label BioHero	Label BioHero
C	Other scanning app	Junker app	https://www.junkerapp.it/

¹ See also <https://nabu-siegel-check.en.softonic.com/android>

D	Online database	Labelinfo (CH)	https://www.labelinfo.ch
E	Other digital solutions	GSES	https://gses-system.com/

How did these initiatives come about?

- A: NABU Siegel-Check was once (in the 2010’s) an externally funded project.
- B: The same applies for Label BioHero, which was produced in the early 2020’s within the Horizon 2020 project AllThings.BioPRO.
 - C: The Junker app was born from the frustration of a group of Italians that compliance with locally applicable waste regulation required a lot of time and effort.
 - D: Labelinfo builds on a 20+-year history of informing consumers about ecolabels. Originally information provided was rather general and static. V2.0 originates from a 2015 decision to develop a more elaborate and robust scheme and scoring system.
 - E: The idea for (what is now) GSES came from a single mother that wondered what food would be good for her newborn child She noted lots of greenwashing and a lack of common understanding and came up with the idea for a meta-scheme.

How do the initiatives generate income – initially and currently (business model)?

- A: NABU Siegel-Check does not generate external income at this time.
- B: The same applies for Label BioHero. The set-up of this app, which has a limited scope in terms of label coverage, and which does not collect/store personal data, hinders the inclusion of extra functionality that could boost its uptake.
 - C: In the early years Junker was bootstrapped². It received no public funding. Winning a prize in a Microsoft competition gave it a boost. Income comes from municipalities that pay an annual subscription fee. In turn they get various benefits: they can optimize costs of recycling while maintaining very high quality of data provided to citizens.
 - D: A range of Swiss organisations, ranging from government (state, regional, local), lotteries, and NGOs fund the activities of Labelinfo on a project basis.
 - E: In the early years GSES was bootstrapped. Some small funding and support from early clients and start-up accelerators. In 2023 external money was raised. Anno 2024 the GSES System is a comprehensive, Software-as-an-Service (“SaaS”) platform that offers various services. Companies, ranging from large to small, from Europe and some beyond, pay for the service.

² “Bootstrapping is the process of building a business from scratch without attracting investment or with minimal external capital. It is a way to finance small businesses by purchasing and using resources at the owner’s expense, without sharing equity or borrowing huge sums of money from banks.” (cite source)

Are the initiatives a (lasting) success, and what are unique selling points?

- A: NABU Siegel-Check is being continued as long as this is technically possible without major costs. NABU does not measure the success or impact of the app.
- B: The scope of Label BioHero s rather specific and limited. The developer maintains the app (without funding), e.g. to showcase it as a working reference. They also provided the 3-CO project with insights and data that the later can build on.
- C: Junker choose to stay away from a model where citizens pay for an app. Citizens are very involved and pressure their municipalities to subscribe. Citizens can recommend functionalities and suggest improvements,
- D: Labelinfo is still busy including further product categories in the advanced scheme. Users do not have to pay for the tool; the interviewee had no data handy on the number of users. An indirect effect (spinoff) of being published at Labelinfo is that certification scheme holders introduce stricter requirements (so that they get a better review)
- E: GSES offers verified rating. They help companies prove their green claims with verified data that builds trust. Dutch Top-3 bank (ABN AMRO) as an early client.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

There are different types of digital solutions that seek to support citizens (and in some cases also professionals) making sustainable purchasing / procurement decisions.

Several initiatives found their origin in frustration that transparent information was not easily available. Spotting a market opportunity, initiators started to fill this, with very little financial resources of their own. For projects that rely on project financing, sustaining -let alone expanding- the results beyond the project duration appears often a challenge.

5 Insights from surveys and focus groups performed in T2.3

In Task 2.3, we utilized a range of research methodologies to gather comprehensive insights on consumer behavior and preferences, which were instrumental in shaping the development of digital solutions in Task 2.4. The methodologies included Computer Assisted Web Interviews (CAWI) and focus group discussions (FGDs).

The main insights from the focus groups regarding digital solutions for bio-based products (BBPs) emphasized the need for tools that enhance consumer understanding and facilitate more informed decision-making. The results also revealed a significant consensus among participants on the development of a mobile app. Most participants agreed that an app would be a highly effective tool for enhancing consumer understanding and facilitating easier access to reliable information on BBPs. Participants highlighted several key areas for improvement:

Information Clarity and Education: There was a strong call for digital platforms that provide clearer and more comprehensive information about what defines a bio-based product and its environmental benefits. This includes a need for better education on the characteristics of BBPs and how they differ from non-bio-based counterparts.

Label and Certification Transparency: Participants expressed concerns about the authenticity and reliability of labels and certifications. They suggested that digital solutions could play a crucial role in verifying these labels and providing transparency about certification standards to build consumer trust.

Product Comparisons and Label Deciphering: There was interest in digital tools that assist consumers in comparing BBPs with conventional products and help decipher complex labels. Such tools would make it easier for consumers to understand product labels and make informed choices based on credible information.

Enhanced Accessibility and Visibility: The focus group discussions also revealed that many consumers face difficulties in locating BBPs in stores. Digital solutions could include features that enhance the visibility and availability of these products, possibly through location-based services that direct consumers to nearby stores or online outlets where they can purchase BBPs.

These insights from the focus groups have directly informed the development of digital mock-ups in Task 2.4, leading to the creation of digital solutions that address these specific consumer needs and concerns.

Also, as a result of these activities, partners decided to target convenience seekers (segment 3) for the development of the digital solutions. This persona is detailed in the next section. Details of these studies can be found in D2.3.

5.1 PERSONA for Mock-up of a digital solution

<p>PERSONA's name: Anna</p> <p>Age: 40 years old</p> <p>Gender: Female</p> <p>Family: Husband Thomas; daughter Olivia (11 years old)</p> <p>Geographical Location: EU country</p> <p>Occupation: Mid-level professional in sectors not directly related to environmental sustainability</p> <p>Education Level: Moderate to high, with a general focus rather than specialization in environmental studies</p> <p>Financial Situation: Perceives her financial status as average</p>	
<p>Psychographics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates intellectual and emotional support for sustainable development, yet there's a notable gap between this support and her actual purchasing behaviours. • Recognizes the importance of sustainability but prioritizes convenience and cost in decision-making. • Exhibits a generally positive attitude towards sustainability in discussions, which doesn't always translate into consistent sustainable consumer behaviour. • Aspires to make sustainable choices, provided they are convenient and integrate smoothly with her current lifestyle. 	
<p>Behavioural Traits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While aware of sustainability issues, her actions do not always align with sustainable practices. • Shows interest in sustainable products but is less diligent in verifying claims or seeking certifications than more proactive advocates. • Prioritizes convenience in shopping, preferring easily accessible and straightforward solutions. 	
<p>Attitude Toward Bio-Based Products:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exhibits a positive attitude towards bio-based products, although tempered by concerns over information clarity, product quality, and economic considerations. Afraid of greenwashing. • Owns bio-based items such as a wooden house and has purchased bio-based cosmetics, shampoo, and baby clothing for a friend's child, paying attention to certificates. However, she has not considered bio-based alternatives for products like plastic toys, furniture, or mattresses. 	
<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness: Experiences confusion about the definition of bio-based products. • Knowledge: Lacks sufficient information on the benefits of bio-based products. • Recognition of Certifications: Faces challenges in recognizing certificates that confirm the biological origin of products. • Social Influence and Support: Limited influence from both close and broader community circles on purchasing and using bio-based products. 	

- Perceived Availability: Experiences difficulty locating bio-based products in stores.
- Media Presence: Information about bio-based products is not as visible as necessary to be adequately informed.
- Personal Benefits and Reputation: The personal benefits and reputation enhancement from using bio-based products are unclear.
- Conscience and Personal Satisfaction: Lacks personal satisfaction from purchasing bio-based products, indicating a disconnect between values and purchasing behaviour.
- Habit Formation: Does not feel that choosing environmentally friendly products is an automatic part of her shopping routine, suggesting a lack of habituation.
- Trust in Certificates: Demonstrates low trust in certificates and is reluctant to use them during purchasing.
- Use of Digital Tools for Information: Shows ambivalence towards using mobile apps or digital solutions to obtain information on bio-based products, highlighting a need for more user-friendly and engaging digital resources.
- Willingness to Pay: Unwilling to pay for digital solutions that would help verify bio-certificates.

6 Mock-up development

Following the co-creation workshops held across 4 countries in T2.3 (detailed in D2.3), extensive consumer input was gathered, leading to the development of three mock-up mobile application solutions tailored to enhance the shopping experience for eco-friendly products. These mock-ups are designed to empower users with the tools they need to make informed, sustainable choices effectively.

1. **First Mock-up Solution - Comprehensive User Engagement:** This app is designed to provide a holistic and interactive experience. It allows users to scan product labels to receive detailed information on eco-friendly features and certifications. Additionally, users can create a profile or browse as guests, facilitating personalized experiences while maintaining privacy for those who prefer it. The app includes functionalities such as searching labels and certifications by name or filters (colour, shape, product category), browsing products added by users or stores, and reading or contributing to consumer reviews. It also suggests eco-friendly products and helps locate the nearest store where such products can be found. Gamification elements like earning badges for scanning items, which can be exchanged for rewards, encourage continued use of the app, making the process of sustainable shopping engaging and rewarding.

Summary of features

With this application, the user can

- create a profile or sign in as guest
- scan labels of products to receive information on product features or certifications
- search labels and certifications by name or with different filters (colour, shape, product category) to receive detailed information
- browse different products added to the application either by an individual user or a store that wants to promote their eco-friendly product
- suggest eco-friendly products to be visible in the app
- Read and give consumer reviews of eco-friendly products
- search the nearest store where products added to the app can be found
- Access additional learning content on eco-friendly products and certification

The use of the application is encouraged with a gamification aspect: earning in-app badges for each item that is scanned. The badges can be exchanged for rewards.

Figure 1 Screenshot of the first mock-up solution at Howspace

1. **Second Mock-up Solution - Store-Centric Features:** This version of the app simplifies the eco-conscious shopping experience by focusing on product discovery and label understanding. It provides functionalities for scanning physical product labels to receive instant information, searching for products by name, and viewing the inventory of promoted eco-friendly products by the shops. To incentivize use,

the app offers discounts through digital coupons, enhancing the value proposition for users making eco-friendly purchases.

Summary of features

In the first page, the application will highlight different labels ("Discover the labels") to the user

With this application, the user can

- create a profile or sign in as guest
- scan labels of physical products to receive information on product features or certifications
- search labels and certifications by name or with different filters (colour, shape, product category) to receive detailed information
- search eco-friendly products by their name
- browse different products added to the application either by an individual user or a store that wants to promote their eco-friendly product
- suggest eco-friendly products to be visible in the app
- read and give consumer reviews of eco-friendly products
- search the nearest store where products added to the app can be found
- access additional learning content on eco-friendly products and certification

The use of the application is encouraged with a gamification aspect: earning in-app badges for each item that is scanned. The badges can be exchanged for rewards.

Figure 2 Screenshot of the second mock-up solution at Howspace

2. **Third Mock-up Solution - Simplified Consumer-Focused Tool:** Tailored for store or shop operators, this app version focuses on promoting eco-friendly products directly from the retail point. It highlights different labels on the main page to educate consumers about various certifications ("Discover the labels"). The app facilitates the search and comparison of products by labels and certifications and allows store owners to showcase their eco-friendly inventory effectively. Users can scan labels for detailed information on product features or certifications, enhancing transparency and trust in the products offered. The app also promotes the use of digital tools for learning about bio-based products, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of sustainable goods.

Each of these mock-ups addresses specific needs and preferences identified during the focus group discussions, such as the demand for clarity in product labelling, the need for easy access to product certifications, and the desire for engaging digital experiences that simplify making eco-friendly choices. By leveraging direct consumer feedback, these app solutions are crafted to not only meet the practical needs of users, but also to enhance their overall experience and satisfaction with sustainable shopping.

Figure 3 Screenshot of the third mock-up solution at Howspace

6.1 Evaluation of the mock-ups

The evaluation of the three digital mock-ups as part of Task 2.3 was conducted to gauge consumer preferences and obtain detailed feedback on their functionality and design, which are aimed at facilitating sustainable purchasing decisions. Here’s a summary of how each mock-up was received by the participants during the evaluation:

Solution 1: Solution 1 was noted for its broad range of features, including a section for learning, gamification elements, and community participation. However, it faced criticism for potentially overwhelming users with too much information displayed at once. Users suggested that the app could benefit from a clearer organization and reduction of text clutter to enhance usability. Despite these issues, the app was recognized for its functionality and engagement potential. Key improvement areas identified included enhancing design clarity and refining icon sizes to make the interface more user-friendly.

Solution 2: This option received the highest approval, praised for its balanced design, intuitive use, and clear navigation. This mock-up was favoured for its straightforward layout and consistent design elements, which contributed to a seamless user experience. Participants suggested minor improvements such as enlarging icons and enhancing visual contrast for better accessibility. Features like price monitoring and more detailed product information were recommended to further aid in decision-

making. Due to its user-friendly design and effective support for sustainable purchasing, Solution 2 was selected for further development.

Solution 3: praised for its balanced design, intuitive use, and clear navigation. This mock-up was favoured for its straightforward layout and consistent design elements, which contributed to a seamless user experience. Participants suggested minor improvements such as enlarging icons and enhancing visual contrast for better accessibility. Features like price monitoring and more detailed product information were recommended to further aid in decision-making.

Following the feedback, the next steps involved refining Solution 2 by incorporating suggested improvements. These enhancements aim to develop an app that not only meets the aesthetic and functional standards expected by users but also effectively supports their sustainable purchasing practices.

7 Requirements definition

Following the evaluation of the mock-ups, we compiled a comprehensive list of requirements based on the feedback received to guide the further development of our digital solution. This list (detailed in table 4) consists of 28 distinct requirements that reflect the needs and suggestions of the participants. Each requirement was carefully assessed to determine its importance, difficulty level, and priority for implementation. This systematic assessment helps ensure that critical features are prioritized, balancing the potential impact on user experience with the feasibility of development. The categorized requirements allow our technical team to strategically allocate resources and focus efforts on enhancements that are most valuable to our users, ensuring that the developed solution is both effective and user-friendly.

Table 4: 3CO App requirement list

Req Id	Requirement description
User Management	
RQ01	Upon entering the app, a splash screen with the 3-CO logo will be displayed.
RQ02	The app will have some functionalities that do not require prior registration: label identification with the camera, access to the labels database.
RQ03.1	The user can fully register, view registration details, modify them, and cancel their account.
RQ03.2	The user can log in.
RQ04	A way to migrate the progress of a Guest user to a 3-CO account must be provided.
Labels	
RQ05	A list of suggested or random labels should be shown each day.
RQ06	Labels should be organized and displayed by category in horizontal lists.
RQ07	Labels should be filterable by SHAPE, COLOR, and CATEGORY, as well as by name or keyword.
RQ08	Filtering should be done by direct selection (without a popup).
RQ09.1	Labels should be able to be scanned from a product. The photo is taken and adjusted to 800x600. The result is displayed on the screen.
RQ09.2	The label identification algorithm (AI) detects and identifies the label received from the UI and returns the information found or "not found."
RQ10	More information about the labels should be shown when clicking on one (DESCRIPTION, ORIGIN, COLORS, KEYWORDS, IMAGE, RATING). This applies to label search in the list as well as scanning.
RQ11	When scanning new labels, the user will have the chance to earn certain badges and/or achievements. The badge should be 512x512.
Products (Engage)	
RQ12	The products section (Engage) will be organized in horizontal rows of product thumbnails divided by product category.

RQ13	Each product thumbnail will include Name, Image, Nearby Shops, Rating, and Short Description.
RQ14	On the Engage home page, the user can post new products.
RQ15	On the Engage home page, the user can filter products by (Name, Category, Rating, Location).
RQ16	On the Engage home page, the user can find Nearby Shops.
RQ17	On the NEARBY SHOPS map, the user can filter by category, with a list of stores sorted in ascending order based on their proximity to the user.
RQ18	The detailed product view will include (Nearby Shops Button, Image, Rating, Name, Description, Labels, Reviews).
RQ19	In the detailed product view, the user can contribute to the product reviews.
RQ20	When the user wants to search for Nearby Shops, the locations of the shops will be displayed on a map.
RQ21	In the Nearby Shops view for a product, a list of stores sorted by distance in ascending order will be shown.
RQ22	Each store will have (NAME, LOCATION, IMAGE, DESCRIPTION, PRODUCTS).
RQ23	To add a product, a form must be completed with: (Name, Image, Store Name (dropdown selection), Location, Categories, Description, and Rating).
Learn	
RQ24	In the Learn section, training and/or informational units will be divided into Videos, Infographics, and Courses.
RQ25	The training units will be organized horizontally.
User activity	
RQ26	The user can access statistical data about their activity, including the number of labels identified, queries, etc.
RQ27	Gamification strategy: the user will receive rewards/badges related to their activity.
Other	
RQ28	Store labels for future use in learning, etc.

8 Graphic design strategy and main design concepts

8.1 App graphic design

For the app design, three distinct, yet cohesively aligned designs had been developed. Each design shares the same goal of delivering a clear and user-friendly interface but offers slightly varied approaches in key areas.

Following this description, a series of images illustrates the winner design concept (see [Annex 2](#) for the two other designs):

Figure 4 - App Start Screen

Figure 5 - Login (Left) | Register (Right)

Figure 6 - Password Recovery (Left) | Change Password (Right)

The following pictures represent the application main content and navigation workflow, explained in boxes:

Figure 7 – Design 2 - Main page (Left) | Explore Labels (Right)

Figure 7 – Design 2 - Main page (Left) | Explore Labels (Right)

Figure 8 – Design 2 - Filters (Left) | Label Info (Right)

Figure 9 - Design 2 - Scan Feature in action

After clicking in "Engage" section in the tab navigation the user is redirected to the following images.

Figure 10 – Design 2 - Products page (Left) | Product Info (Right)

Figure 11 – Design 2 - Nearby locations (Left) | Nearby product locations (Right)

After clicking on the desired shop, the user can see all products listed for it, as in the image below. Along with the image about the shop information, we can see a simple form to post new products.

Figure 12 – Design 2 - Shop info and products (Left) | Add new product (Right)

The user will be able to learn a variety of new things related to the eco-environment, after clicking on learn section in navigation tab.

Figure 13 – Design 2 - Learn Page

8.2 User interface aspects and decisions

During the decision-making process, Enide played a pivotal role by sharing a detailed questionnaire among project partners, which gathered essential feedback to guide the design choices for the application. The questionnaire focused on evaluating three distinct design concepts, asking partners to provide input on various key aspects such as color scheme, layout structure, filtering options, and gamification elements. This collaborative feedback process enabled the design team to make informed decisions that align with user preferences and project goals.

The questionnaire explored the following UI aspects in depth:

- **Color Scheme:** Partners were asked to rank different colour options based on their perceived impact on usability and aesthetic appeal. The chosen colour palette reflects the preferences of the majority, focusing on creating a visually appealing yet functional interface.
- **Layout Structure:** Questions about layout assessed the ease of navigation and clarity of information display. Feedback highlighted a preference for a clean, minimalistic layout that prioritizes readability and accessibility. As a result, design adjustments were made to improve spacing, menus, and element hierarchy.
- **Filtering Options:** Given the application's functionality, filtering options were a significant focus. Partners evaluated two different filtering mechanisms to determine which would provide the most efficient user experience. Based on feedback, the final design includes a user-friendly, collapsible filter menu that enhances ease of access without cluttering the main interface.
- **Gamification Elements:** Gamification was explored to increase user engagement. Partners rated various gamification features, such as progress tracking and rewards for specific actions. Based on this feedback, a limited set of badges were integrated to encourage user interaction without overwhelming the core functionality. (See the badges in Annex 3: Designed badges)

The responses and preferences gathered in the questionnaire were systematically analysed to identify common themes and priorities, leading to a refined design that balances functionality with aesthetic appeal. Detailed results from the questionnaire, as well as specific partner feedback, are included in D2.3, showing the direct influence of the questionnaire findings on the final design.

In summary, this participative approach ensured that the application's UI design reflects the collective vision of the project partners and addresses the diverse needs of its intended users. The final design serves as a blend of collaborative input and best practices in UI design, aiming to create an engaging, user-friendly experience.

9 Architecture, technical design and implementation

9.1 General architecture picture and main technical design concepts

The architecture of the app (Check Figure 14) is designed around microservices to ensure modularity, scalability, and flexibility. Here's an overview of the architecture and its core design principles:

The system is based on a microservices architecture, where each service is designed to fulfil a specific function and is maintained in a modular and independent manner. This separation allows each service to be scaled, updated, and maintained without affecting other parts of the application, thus promoting greater flexibility and efficiency

Figure 14 – General architecture

The main services include the API Service, which handles all external requests from the mobile client, such as user authentication, request verification, and data processing. In addition, this service interacts with an AI service for tag recognition and with a database to store user records and progress on badges or achievements. On the other hand, the AI Service is dedicated to image detection, using the YOLOv8 model for real-time tag recognition. This design allows the AI model to be updated without affecting the other components of the system. In terms of storage, a database service (PostgreSQL) hosted on AWS RDS has been implemented, which centralizes and secures user data, badge thresholds, and scan history, ensuring high availability, security, and consistency.

The architecture is based on key technical concepts, such as the design of a RESTful API in the API service. This is reflected in the clear definition of endpoints that allow users to perform actions such as

scanning tags, tracking their badges, and querying statistics. This RESTful structure establishes a clean and predictable interface that facilitates both interaction with the mobile application and future integrations with third parties.

For image recognition, the AI service benefits from the capabilities of YOLOv8, a high-performance deep learning model optimized for tag detection. The accuracy and speed of the model offer a real-time response to tag scanning, improving the user experience by allowing instant feedback.

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For image recognition, the AI service benefits from the capabilities of YOLOv8, a high-performance deep learning model optimized for tag detection. The accuracy and speed of the model offer a real-time response to tag scanning, improving the user experience by allowing instant feedback.

Finally, the progress tracking system is gamified, with a badge or achievement structure designed to encourage user participation. This reward system provides a rich user experience by incentivizing interaction through progressively unlocking levels and achievable goals.

Figure 15 AWS infrastructure architecture

The AWS infrastructure, including ECS for container orchestration, RDS for the PostgreSQL database, and CloudWatch for monitoring. This infrastructure setup supports high availability, resilience, and scalability while reducing operational overhead.

10 User interface

10.1 Frameworks, baseline software, etc

To maximize accessibility and broaden the app's user base, Enide selected Ionic as the primary multi-platform development framework. Ionic, combined with Angular 18+ and Capacitor, allows for a single codebase that can be deployed seamlessly on both iOS and Android platforms. This strategy minimizes development time and ensures consistency across devices while leveraging Capacitor's capabilities to integrate native functionality smoothly.

10.2 Features description from technical point of view

- **Offline Labels Database:** To support offline use, Enide includes an embedded SQLite database within the app, storing label data such as images, names, descriptions, and ratings. This offline functionality ensures that users can access essential information regardless of network availability.
- **Labels Image Recognition:** The app's user interface enables users to take photos of product labels, which are then sent to a server for analysis. Once processed, the server returns a report containing relevant product and label details, which is displayed to the user. This image recognition feature enhances user engagement by providing real-time, accessible information about products.
- **Product Ecosystem:** Users can interact with a comprehensive product ecosystem within the app, allowing them to add, search, review, and check various products. This feature fosters a community-centered approach, providing users with a space to explore and share information about different products.
- **Learning Materials:** The app also offers a curated library of educational resources, including videos, courses, and infographics. These materials, provided by the consortium, supply users with additional information on topics like sustainable consumption and eco-label standards, contributing to a richer learning experience.

10.3 Components and interactions

The user interface is structured around modular components that ensure both ease of use and high engagement. Key components include:

- **Interactive Buttons and Navigation:** These facilitate smooth transitions between screens, with intuitive controls to enhance the user experience.
- **Camera and Image Processing Interface:** Integrated directly into the app, this component allows users to capture label images easily, automatically linking to the server's image recognition system.

- **Database Viewer and Search Function:** Enables users to browse the offline labels database, with quick search functionality for efficient access to label information.
- **Learning Materials Interface:** This component organizes educational content in a user-friendly layout, ensuring that users can easily access and view the provided resources.

11 Cloud/Backend

11.1 Frameworks, baseline software, etc

The project is built on a solid foundation of frameworks and tools carefully selected to ensure optimal performance, scalability, and a smooth development experience:

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The system backend is developed in Flask, a Python microframework that enables the construction REST API. Every endpoint has been designed with a different use case for the application, receiving user information, interacting with the database, and managing the flow of rewards. Moreover, Flask-RESTful has been used—a Flask extension that makes it easier to organize REST endpoints and enhances the structure and error handling of APIs. For data management in this system, SQLAlchemy is used as an ORM.

The main database is PostgreSQL, hosted on AWS RDS. AWS RDS ensures high availability of the database

Docker and Docker-Compose are used for storage and containers. Each service operates inside a Docker container that wraps up the environment with its dependencies for fast and reproducible deployments. Docker Compose, at the level of local setup, is applied to orchestrate several services. Whereas in production, the containers run on AWS ECS that will enable automatic scaling depending on the traffic and workload of the application.

In the application, the model applied for machine learning is YOLOv8 Object Detection, specialized in recognizing labels of things in images. It means that for detection, the accuracy will be increased and a real-time user experience will be provided.

11.2 Features description from technical point of view

The app's core technical features are built to create an engaging user experience while ensuring stability, security, and seamless interaction between the mobile interface, backend API, and AI services. Here's a breakdown of these key components:

The app's core technical features are built to create an engaging user experience while ensuring stability, security, and seamless interaction between the mobile interface, backend API, and AI services. Here's a breakdown of these key components:

One of the key features of the app is a scan-and-detect flow where the user would be able to scan labels by sending pictures of these labels to a specific REST API endpoint. That endpoint receives an incoming request, verifies the received content, and then logs every attempt to scan something. Later, this API will need to interact with the AI service for image processing to identify a certain label.

Label recognition uses the YOLOv8 model, specially trained with high-precision detection of sustainable labels. It uses a high confidence threshold in order not to get many false positives and to detect precisely the labels within uploaded images by users.

The gamification of this system comes with a Badge/ Reward system. Badges are granted to the user through collected scans, following pre-defined thresholds in every category of a label-for example, Cleaning Products, Food, and Textiles. These thresholds provide levels for badges: bronze, silver, and gold, progressively unlocked if the user meets the required number of scans in each category.

In particular, the API provides badge monitoring specific for each user, working on progress in the different badge categories. Once thresholds are reached, automatic changes to user status enable higher badge levels that will directly reflect real-time status.

The backend then gathers detailed metrics on every scan, including but not limited to the following: timestamp, tag category, and result of the scan-either valid or invalid. In this way, it is possible to show in the application interface the exact number of total scans, valid scans, and failed attempts via the statistics. These statistics are recalculated dynamically by the API as new scans are made by the user, updating his progress towards badges in real time.

With respect to internal service communication, every image analysis request is handled by an AI microservice that interacts directly with the API. All this separation will mean it is scalable and modular; hence, each microservice will be able to be managed independently. Also, internal communication among the microservices is performed using API calls in a secure way inside the AWS ECS ecosystem to minimize security risks and maintain data integrity.

11.3 AI model

Different approaches and technologies were explored to deal with the challenge. After a wide research study, the YOLOv8 algorithm was chosen for its advantages in terms of speed, accuracy, and being able to find several objects within an image.

In the first phase, several options were explored, including TensorFlow and other popular libraries. Traditional image classification algorithms were also considered. However, after extensive research, YOLOv8 was chosen due to its advantages in speed, accuracy, and ability to detect multiple objects.

After this initial definition of baseline tools for building the AI model, the following steps were applied:

1. Data Collection: An image dataset was collected that included a variety of labels. Initially, approximately 2000 images were used, which were expanded to a range of 8000 to 10,000 images using data augmentation techniques.

2. Training:

The YOLOv8 model was trained using the prepared dataset. Training was carried out on an Nvidia 3080 card and multiple hyperparameter adjustments were made to optimize performance.

3. Evaluation: The model was tested with an independent validation dataset. The performances that were obtained after running the model were encouraging, achieving an accuracy of 82%.

Results

The developed model provided an accuracy of 82% in label classification, which outperformed previous models by 15%, while reducing the processing time of each image by 20%. These results prove the effectiveness of the proposed method and open a new perspective for possible practical applications in numerous fields.

11.4 Architecture, Components and interactions

The application is structured as a microservices-based system, comprising several independent yet interlinked components. The architecture promotes modularity, scalability, and ease of deployment.

11.5 Interface with UI

The API is designed to efficiently interact with the mobile app's UI, providing a dynamic and real-time experience for users, using Http request protocol: The API microservice is in charge of acting like the main endpoint between the mobile application and the backend. It will process the HTTP requests, handle authentication, perform basic image validation, manage scan management, among other things. This microservice enables session management by a user, validation of the scan attempts, logging of those, requesting AI microservice to recognize tags, and real-time updating of badge statistics and progress. The AI microservice focuses on the recognition of tags, utilizing the YOLOv8 model. It returns its results with a certain level of confidence. This service is optimized to be both fast and accurate, thus ensuring that response times will be quick and the interaction with the API smooth.

Database: PostgreSQL on AWS RDS; it stores user records, badge thresholds, scan history, and statistics. Centrally stored data provides high availability, consistency, and fast query capability, maintaining the app in real time.

Scanning Flow: An image is first scanned by the user and uploaded to the application. It then undergoes validation and is passed on to the AI service for processing. It saves the detection result in the database that will check badge progress. Users can reflect achievements in the app. Metrics of real-time badge progression, with scan results, are shown on the mobile interface. All microservices are containerized with Docker and deployed on AWS ECS, with all features like scalability, load balancing, and monitoring via AWS CloudWatch. The database is made secure on AWS RDS with SSL and managed access rules to maximum effect.

11.6 Deployment aspects

To facilitate the deployment and management of the application, a clear and modular is followed:

- The development environment uses Docker containers to replicate the production environment. Deployment on AWS ECS allows containers to be managed and scaled according to the workload.
- For monitoring and scalability, AWS CloudWatch has been configured, which offers real-time metrics and alerts, making it easy to detect problems and adjust ECS capacity according to user demand, thus ensuring a smooth experience.

12 Data description and workflows

The application processes data related to users, scans, badges (achievements), and image analysis for tag detection. Here is a detailed description of the data and workflows:

12.1 Data sets

The app uses four main data sets to manage the image detection, progress tracking, and user reward system functionality:

Users: Registered and authenticated user data contains basic information for authentication and personalization of the experience:

ID: Unique user identifier.

Name: Username.

Email: Unique email for communication and authentication.

Password Hash: Encrypted password.

Scans: Information from image scans performed by each user, used to detect tags and assess progress toward achievements.

- **User ID:** ID of the user who performed the scan.
- **Tag:** Category or tag detected in the image scan (such as "Food" or "Textiles").
- **Date/Time:** Exact moment of the scan recorded in timestamp format.
- **Badges:** Data representing user achievements and progress, organized by categories and levels.
- **Category:** Area or topic of the badge (such as "Food" or "Textiles").
- **Badge Level:** Current level of the badge (e.g. bronze, silver, or gold) based on thresholds.
- **Unlocked At:** Date and time the badge was unlocked.
- **Recognition Results:** Data returned by the AI model that includes the tags recognized in the scanned images.

- **Tags:** Set of tags that the recognition model identified.

- **Confidence:** How certain the AI is about each tag, if available.

12.2 Information flows

The information flow in the system follows a logical sequence that allows user authentication, image analysis, and reward delivery:

User Registration and Authentication Flow

The user sends a POST with name, email, and password to the API. The API encrypts the password and stores it in the user database. For login, the user receives a JSON Web Token (JWT) after authentication to keep the session secure and private.

Image Detection Flow

The user, once authenticated, sends an image for analysis at the `/v2/api/detect` endpoint. The API receives the image and forwards it to the 3comodel service for tag processing using the YOLOv8 model. The 3comodel service analyses the image and returns the tags found. The API saves the scan to the database and checks if the detected tags meet the thresholds for a new badge. If the scan unlocks a badge, it is saved, and the updated list of badges is returned to the user.

Badge Unlocking Flow

The API compares the accumulated scans with the thresholds for each badge category. If the threshold is met, a new badge is generated, and the API updates the database. A notification with the list of unlocked badges is sent to the user, consolidating their progress.

Badge Recovery

The user can access the list of their badges through the `/v2/api/user_badges` endpoint. The API queries the database to obtain and send the updated badges, including category, level, and unlock date. This information flow allows for efficient data management and a real-time response to user actions, while maintaining accuracy in image recognition and reward granting.

13 Conclusion

The culmination of Task 2.4 within the 3-CO project has successfully delivered a state-of-the-art mobile application, seamlessly blending advanced technology with user-centric design to foster sustainable consumer behavior. This initiative started with a thorough analysis of existing digital solutions and involved extensive interactions with industry providers and consumers through surveys and workshops, setting a solid foundation for development.

Technologically, the application features a scalable microservices architecture utilizing Docker and Amazon ECS, ensuring robust performance and reliability. The integration of a mobile API and an image processing service supports effective product recognition, while a PostgreSQL database securely manages user data and interactions. The implementation of a badge system, incorporating JWT for authentication, enhances user engagement by rewarding sustainable choices.

The AI-driven label recognition model, particularly the YOLOv8 classifier, has shown impressive results, underscoring the project's commitment to technological excellence. This model's success paves the way for potential future enhancements, such as incorporating active learning to further improve accuracy and integrating additional AI systems to broaden functionality.

The front-end development was guided by feedback from the consortium on initial Figma mock-ups, leading to the selection and refinement of the second design using the Ionic and Angular frameworks. This approach facilitated the creation of a versatile, multi-platform application tailored to meet user needs, including the integration of a robust offline database and custom reward badges that significantly enhance the user experience.

Despite several challenges, such as integrating the offline database and developing custom reward badges, the development team overcame these obstacles through meticulous planning and iterative testing. This not only ensured the stability and cohesiveness of the application but also equipped it with features that make user interactions seamless, enjoyable, and productive.

In conclusion, the collaborative efforts of the development teams have yielded a digital solution that not only meets the specific needs of the consortium but also sets a new benchmark for future digital tools aimed at promoting sustainable consumption. The ongoing refinement and expansion of this application will continue to support the sustainability agenda, encouraging a broader shift toward environmentally responsible consumer practices. The methodologies and insights derived from this task provide a comprehensive framework for embedding sustainability into digital consumer platforms, heralding a new era of eco-conscious technological innovation.

Annex 1: Existing digital solutions

Think Dirty

Features

Think Dirty is a mobile application that helps consumers make informed decisions about the personal care products they use.

Functionalities

Some of the key functionalities of Think Dirty include:

- **Barcode Scanning:** The app's barcode scanner allows users to easily scan product barcodes to access ingredient information and ratings.
- **Search Functionality:** Users can search for personal care products by name, brand, or category.
- **Ingredient Information:** Think Dirty provides detailed information about each ingredient in a product, including its function, potential health concerns, and scientific studies.
- **Personalized Lists:** Users can create lists of their favourite products, as well as products they would like to try in the future.
- **Clean Alternatives:** The app recommends cleaner and safer alternative products based on the user's search history and product ratings.
- **Push Notifications:** Users can receive push notifications when products on their lists are updated with new ingredient information.

Revenue Model

Think Dirty generates revenue through affiliate marketing partnerships with companies that sell products on the app's platform. The app receives a commission on each sale made through its platform.

Testing

Think Dirty's mobile application is available for download on both the Apple App Store and Google Play Store. The app has a simple and user-friendly interface, with a barcode scanner that allows users to easily scan and find information about products. The app's product search functionality is also easy to use, allowing users to search for products by name, brand, or category. The Think Dirty® methodology is focused on helping consumers identify potential risks associated with their personal care products. Instead of using the widely used practice of "greenwashing," which considers the environmental or social responsibility of a product's manufacturer in its assessment, Think Dirty® solely focuses on the chemical content of the products. As an independent company, Think Dirty® is committed to assessing the possible impact of a product on an individual's health and bases its ratings methodology on publicly available data released by non-profit and government agencies in North America. The Chemistry Team and Advisory Board at Think Dirty® evaluate the overall risk of a product based on the potential health impacts of its published ingredients.

THINK DIRTY. SHOP VERIFIED BRANDS AWARDS TOP 10 FOR BRAND PARTNERS

4.5K BRANDS
1.9M PRODUCTS SUBMITTED
26.2M UNIQUE SCANS

BEAUTY BOX! ★★★★★ SEE OUR REVIEWS

Fresh new products coming your way, get the best in clean beauty! Here are the top-ranked products in the industry. Fawn over new products, holy grails, and upgrade your shelfie.

Top 10 Hair Removal Aftercare Products

View all

Top 10 Eyeliners

View all

For the selected clean beauty, personal care, household products, baby and maternity, feminine products, and sexual wellness products brands from around the world, the company offers a verification service in which the ingredient list of each brand is carefully reviewed in their database. After inspection, if the brand passes, it is listed with a checkmark icon to let users know that the ingredient lists have been carefully vetted by the company.

There is an 'Award' section listing the best products, divided by category (skin care, body, hair, etc.), voted by Think Dirty users.

Below is the simulation with the application (via Android device). I downloaded the app on both Android and Apple devices. On the Android device it does not work, so the simulation was conducted on Apple.

The app allows you to search for a product using the barcode scanner, search by insertion, list of ingredients.

I searched via barcode for three products I had on hand: a hair product, a body cream and cosmetics. The hair cream and the hair product produced no results, but I was able to enter them into their database via a form.

The cosmetic produced results, but the app does not give much information, in fact it gives their score, recommendations and the link to buy it. If you want to see the list of ingredients with whether they are dangerous or not, you have to buy the premium plan (see photo of costs).

Then I did a simulation with one of the companies' products of the 10 product categories selected for this research, in this case Aveda of the shampoo products. In this case there was a user evaluation, in addition to that of the app.

Screenshots of the app

Overall perception and additional information

Think Dirty has a rating of 4.5 stars on the Apple App Store based on over 5,000 ratings, and a rating of 4.2 stars on the Google Play Store based on over 3,000 ratings. The app has received praise for its user-friendly interface and ability to provide consumers with information about the safety of the products they use. However, some critics have raised concerns about the accuracy of the app's ingredient ratings and its potential to contribute to "chemophobia" or the fear of all synthetic chemicals.

In my opinion, Think Dirty is an ambitious and well-designed project, it is explained in detail how it works on the web page and the application is user-friendly. The problem arises when it cannot find all the products and once found you have to pay to get all the information. Honestly, compared to other applications in the same sector it still has something to improve, especially the transparency of the information.

EWG Healthy Living

Features

EWG Healthy Living is a website and mobile application that provides consumers with information about the safety of personal care products, cleaning products, and food.

Functionalities

Some of the key functionalities of EWG Healthy Living include:

- **Product Database:** The app's database allows users to search for personal care products, cleaning products, and foods and view their safety ratings.
- **Product Ratings:** EWG provides ratings for each product based on the potential health risks associated with the ingredients it contains.
- **Ingredient Information:** EWG provides detailed information about each ingredient in a product, including its function, potential health concerns, and scientific studies.
- **Clean Alternatives:** The app recommends cleaner and safer alternative products based on the user's search history and product ratings.
- **Personalized Lists:** Users can create lists of their favourite products, as well as products they would like to try in the future.
- **Blog and News Articles:** EWG publishes articles and news stories related to personal care products, cleaning products, and food safety.

Revenue Model

EWG is a non-profit organization that operates through grants and donations. The Healthy Living app and website are provided as a public service to help consumers make informed decisions about the products they use. Instead, their revenue comes from a variety of sources, including grants and donations from individuals, corporations, and foundations.

Testing

Below is the simulation via application on an Apple device. The application is not downloadable in our territory, so I used a US account to do a simulation. I tried scanning the products I had but none produced any results, probably because they are not in the US, but it is possible to enter them manually. I then did a simulation with a skin care product, and the app provided a lot of information, including

their score, the list of ingredients and their rating according to their hazard to humans, and the presence of the ESW mark recognising the product's environmental friendliness.

My perceptions and additional information

Google Play: 3.5* and 6.56K reviews; Apple Store: 3.4* and 691 Ratings.

The website has a simple and user-friendly interface, with a search bar that allows users to search for products by name, brand, or category. They combined their most popular resources, including the Skin Deep cosmetics database. The mobile app has a similar interface, with a barcode scanner that allows users to easily scan and find information about products. Both the website and mobile app provide users with valuable information about the safety of the products they use. Overall, EWG Healthy Living can be a helpful tool for consumers who want to make more informed decisions about the products they use, but it is important to use it in conjunction with other sources of information and to understand its limitations.

In my opinion the app is very well made, their evaluation system is also complete. The only problem is that it cannot be fully applied in Europe, as the app is not downloadable in our territory and does not include many products that we use in our daily lives.

Buycott

Features

Buycott is a mobile app that allows consumers to make informed purchasing decisions based on their values and beliefs. The app allows users to scan barcodes of products and view information about the company that produces them. The app also allows users to join campaigns or create their own to support causes they care about. For example, a user can join a campaign that supports fair labor practices, and the app will inform the user if a product they scan is made by a company that has been criticized for unfair labor practices.

Functionalities

- Barcode scanner to scan products and view company information
- Create and join campaigns to support causes and view company scorecards
- Browse and follow campaigns created by others
- Get alerts and updates on campaign progress
- Connect with friends and build a community of like-minded consumers

Revenue Model

Buycott is a free app and does not charge for any of its features. The company generates revenue through donations and grants, as well as through partnerships with organizations that share their values.

Here all paid plans, divided into basic, developer and startup categories.

Simulation

The Buycott app allows users to scan barcodes and view company information, join or create campaigns, and connect with a community of like-minded shoppers. The app is available for download on both the Apple Store and Google Play Store.

Here is one of the initiatives promoted by Buycott that people can join, in this case 'Shop Women-Friendly Companies to Promote Equality'.

Shop Women-Friendly Companies to Promote Equality

Women's Rights • 9 companies

Eighty-five percent of women make the purchasing decisions for their households, yet the companies they're buying from are often paying them less, creating sexist advertising, or offering poor parental leave policies. Your dollar is your vote, so why not vote for companies that treat you and other women right?

The Buy Up Index has created a list of companies that serve women well through leadership programs, paid parental leave, stereotype-breaking ads, and social good campaigns. Use your purchasing power to reward the companies that help women. Give them your vote.

Join the Campaign

24,350 members

Only 5,650 away from 30,000

Name

Email

(I'm joining because... (optional))

Share with my friends

In this case, the simulation was conducted in their web site with the brand 'Aveda', from the category 'Shampoo'. It is possible to search for a product by UPC (Universal Product Code), Product Name and Brand Name.

buycott Brand Search brand name Barcode API Campaigns

Home Aveda UPCs

Product categories: Balms & Moisturizers, Bar Soap, Blush, Body and Foot Scrub, Body Fat Monitors, Body Scrubs, Body Sprays, Body Washes, Chemical Hair Dyes, Cleansers, Conditioners, Conditioners, Creams, Creams, Creams, Gels & See More

Likely owner: Aveda Corporation

		UPC 018084854877 Aveda Dry Remedy Moisturizing Conditioner
		UPC 087558743443 Aveda Brilliant Universal Styling Creme
		UPC 018084854853 Aveda Dry Remedy Moisturizing Shampoo
		UPC 018084851043 Aveda Men Pure-formance Liquid Pomade
		UPC 018084826577 Aveda Caribbean Therapy Body Creme
		UPC 018084848781 Aveda Outer Peace Foaming Cleanser 4.2 oz.
		UPC 940356645848 Aveda Damage Remedy Restructuring Shampoo
		UPC 018084850961 Aveda Men Pure-formance Exfoliating Shampoo
		UPC 018084850930 Aveda Men Pure-formance Shampoo
		UPC 963041812639 Aveda Botanical Kinetics Purifying Gel Cleanser

UPC 087558743443

Aveda Brilliant Universal Styling Creme

See on Ebay

Brand	Aveda
Manufacturer	Aveda Corporation
UPC	087558743443
EAN	0087558743443
Country	U.S. and Canada
Category	Health & Personal Care > Personal Care > Hair Care > Styling Gel/Lotion
Last Scan	Apr 4 2023 at 8:23 AM
GS1 Name	Aveda Corporation
GS1 Address	5300 RECKER HIGHWAY Winter Haven FL US
Description	No description for 087558743443
Barcode	

Apart from a general product description, it provides no information on sustainability and does not categorise it as bio or non-bio.

I could not install the app on my Android device because it says 'This app is not available for your device because it was created for an older version of Android.'

Join Campaigns

Join crowd-sourced campaigns to get behind causes you care about

Shop Smart

Scan barcodes when shopping to learn product history & make an informed decision

Speak Up

Get your message across by notifying the product owners of your decision

Overall perception and additional information

Boycott has generally received positive reviews on both the Apple Store and Google Play Store, with an average rating of 4.4 out of 5 stars on the Apple Store and 4.3 out of 5 stars on the Google Play Store. Many users appreciate the app's ability to provide transparency about the companies behind the products they buy and support causes they care about. Some users have noted that the app can be slow to load or buggy at times, but overall the app is well-received.

It is interesting that Boycott supports good causes by creating 'boycotts', thereby bringing together a large community of people fighting against change.

Giki

Features

Giki is a mobile app that helps users make sustainable and ethical purchasing decisions. The app provides information on the environmental and social impact of products, as well as their nutritional value. Giki aims to empower consumers to make more informed choices and encourage companies to become more sustainable and socially responsible.

Functionalities

- Scan barcodes to view product information and sustainability ratings
- Search for products and view detailed information on their sustainability and nutritional value
- Browse categories and find more sustainable and ethical options
- Create and share shopping lists with friends and family
- Set personal sustainability goals and track progress
- Get alerts and updates on product sustainability and ethical issues

Revenue Model

Giki generates revenue through partnerships with companies that are committed to sustainability and social responsibility. The company also offers a paid subscription service that provides more detailed information and analysis on products.

Testing

Their badges draw on a number of different sources such as product information, government guidelines, and scientific research. **Green** for sustainability, **red** for health and **blue** for fairness.

Their aim is to provide easy-to-understand badges as well as transparency about how they award those badges so users can choose which badges are most relevant to them.

They also look to continuously improve Impact Score® Shopping to help support their users in their quest to buy more sustainable and healthy products. They know they will never be perfect, but they hope that by constantly listening to their users and improving, they will get better and better over time. Users can review the badges below to see the rationale and methodology for how badges are awarded. Oversight of changes to their methodology, and the addition of new badges, is performed by Impact Score® Shopping’s Advisory Board.

Methodology

Organic -

Organic means lower levels of pesticides, no manufactured herbicides or artificial fertilisers, higher levels of animal welfare, and more environmentally sustainable management of farmland and the natural environment.

A green badge means the product passes our organic criteria which is based on certification by independent organisations. A grey badge means it does not and it is in a category where organic certification is relevant.

Organic certification standards aim to protect the environment, maximise use of renewable resources and minimise pollution while protecting local wildlife and animal welfare too.

We look for Soil Association, EU Organic, Organic Farmers and Growers and USDA certification in Food and Drink. We also look for GOTS certification for a small number of non-food products.

Methodology

No chemicals of concern -

Contains fewer chemicals that are associated with irritation. Also avoids chemicals that have been linked to health or environmental risks.

A red badge means the product does not contain any ingredients on Impact Score® Shopping’s list of chemicals of concern. A grey badge means we found one, or more, chemicals of concern. The badge applies to skin and haircare products which includes cosmetics and personal care items.

Some chemicals in personal products cause skin irritation for some people. Others have been linked to cancer, hormone disruption and infertility. Impact Score® Shopping’s checklist has been compiled from a number of sources which cite common chemicals of concern including the Campaign for [Safe Cosmetics](#), [Breast Cancer UK](#) and the [David Suzuki Foundation](#).

Due to different names for the same ingredient, abbreviations and other issues Impact Score® Shopping’s list will necessarily evolve over time. Always check the label if there are particular chemicals which you are concerned about.

The No Chemicals of Concern badge is awarded to skin and haircare products which do not contain any ingredients on Impact Score® Shopping’s chemicals of concern list.

Apart from the methodology used, the webpage does not provide sufficient information. Below is the simulation with their application. The Giki app allows users to scan barcodes and view sustainability ratings and information on products.

I could not install the app on my Android device because it says 'This app is not available for your device because it was created for an older version of Android.'

Overall perception and additional information

Giki has generally received positive reviews on both the Apple Store and Google Play Store, with an average rating of 4.5 out of 5 stars on the Apple Store and 4.4 out of 5 stars on the Google Play Store. Users appreciate the app's ability to provide transparency and information on the products they buy and its focus on sustainability and social responsibility. Some users have noted that the app can be slow to load or has limited product information, but overall the app is well-received.

The web page, apart from giving information on the type of methodology they use (very well explained and detailed), does not give the possibility to search for products, so one has to use the application.

Skin Deep Features

Skin Deep is an online database and tool created by the Environmental Working Group (EWG) that provides information on the safety and potential health hazards of personal care products and cosmetics. The database provides ratings and detailed information on ingredients in products, as well as information on potential health hazards and regulatory information.

Functionalities

- Search for personal care products and cosmetics by name, brand, or product type
- View ratings and information on the safety and potential health hazards of products
- View detailed information on the ingredients in products, including potential health hazards and regulatory information
- Create a personal profile to save favourite products and searches
- Access articles and resources on personal care product safety and health

Revenue Model

The Skin Deep database has been a valuable resource for consumers and advocates concerned about the safety of personal care products and cosmetics. The database is regularly updated and provides detailed information on ingredients and potential health hazards, as well as regulatory information. While there is no mobile app for Skin Deep, the database is easily accessible through the Environmental Working Group's website and has received positive reviews and recognition for its contributions to consumer health and safety.

Testing

The Skin Deep database is available online and can be accessed through the Environmental Working Group's website (**EWG**). To use the functionality of the Skin Deep database, one must use the web page, whereas if one wants to use an application, one must download and install the EWG Healthy Living application, in which one can do essentially what is shown below via the web, but with less functionality.

Users can search for products, view ratings and information, and create a personal profile to save information and searches.

In this case, the simulation was conducted with the brand 'RMS Beauty', from the category 'Cosmetics'.

Via the webpage, it is possible to search for the brand or product, providing different results. Once you have selected the desired product, you have the general evaluation given by EWG, list of ingredients with explanation, brand info and certificates. It also tells where you can buy the product.

2 RMS Beauty Beauty Oil (2018 formulation)

Data Availability: **Limited**

INGREDIENT CONCERNS LABEL INFORMATION CERTIFICATIONS

Ingredient concerns

See how this product scores for common concerns.

- **LOW** Cancer
- **HIGH** Allergies & Immunotoxicity
- **MODERATE** Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity
- **LOW** Use Restrictions

Ingredient scores

Ingredients are scored based on their formulation and concentration in this product. Click on an ingredient for more information.

1	SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS (JOJOBA) SEED OIL Appeared as: GOLDEN SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS (JOJOBA) SEED OIL	Data Availability: Limited	+
3	ROSA MOSCHATA (MUSK ROSE) SEED OIL Appeared as: ROSA MOSQUETA (ROSEHIP) SEED OIL	Data Availability: Limited	+
1	SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS (JOJOBA) SEED OIL Appeared as: HERBS INFUSED IN GOLDEN SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS SEED , (JOJOBA)	Data Availability: Limited	+
1	HYPERICUM PERFORATUM (ST. JOHN'S WORT)	Data Availability: Fair	+
1	HORSETAIL (EQUISETUM ARVENSE) Appeared as: EQUISETUM ARVENSE (HORSETAIL)	Data Availability: Limited	+
1	CALENDULA OFFICINALIS (POT MARIGOLD) Appeared as: CALENDULA OFFICINALIS (MARIGOLD)	Data Availability: Limited	+

WHERE TO BUY

RMS BEAUTY

AMAZON

As an Amazon Associate, EWG earns from qualifying purchases.

CATEGORY

[Facial Moisturizer/Treatment](#)

BRAND

[rms beauty](#)

DATA LAST UPDATED

October 2018

1 SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS (JOJOBA) SEED OIL Data Availability: Limited —

Appeared as: GOLDEN SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS (JOJOBA) SEED OIL

FUNCTION(S) hair conditioning agent, skin-conditioning agent - occlusive, emollient, hair conditioning, skin conditioning, viscosity controlling

[LEARN MORE ABOUT THIS INGREDIENT](#)

3 ROSA MOSCHATA (MUSK ROSE) SEED OIL Data Availability: Limited —

Appeared as: ROSA MOSQUETA (ROSEHIP) SEED OIL

FUNCTION(S) skin-conditioning agent - emollient, emollient, skin conditioning

CONCERNS

- Allergies/immunotoxicity (high)
- Non-reproductive organ system toxicity (moderate)

[LEARN MORE ABOUT THIS INGREDIENT](#)

2 RMS Beauty Beauty Oil (2018 formulation)

Data Availability: Limited

INGREDIENT CONCERNS LABEL INFORMATION CERTIFICATIONS

Ingredients from packaging:

*Golden Simmondsia Chinensis (Jojoba) Seed Oil, *Rosa Mosqueta (Rosehip) Seed Oil, Herbs Infused in *Golden Simmondsia Chinensis (Jojoba) Seed Oil: *Hypericum Perforatum (St. John’s Wort), *Equisetum Arvense (Horsetail), *Calendula Officinalis (Marigold), *Hemidesmus Indicus (Country Sarsaparilla), *Curcuma Longa (Turmeric), *Withania Somnifera (Ashwagandha), *Glycyrrhiza Glabra (Licorice), *Olea Europaea (Olive Leaf), **Buriti (Mauritia Flexuosa) Oil, *Calophyllum Inophyllum (Tamanu) Seed Oil, Tocopherol (non-GMO), *Vanilla Planifolia (Vanilla) Extract

Directions from packaging:

2 RMS Beauty Beauty Oil (2018 formulation)

Data Availability: Limited

INGREDIENT CONCERNS LABEL INFORMATION CERTIFICATIONS

Product’s animal testing policies

Some cosmetics companies have taken People for the Ethical Treatment of Animals and Leaping Bunny animal-testing pledges. For consumers who are concerned about companies’ policies on animal testing, Skin Deep reports this information.

Unknown

Leading international certifiers PETA and Leaping Bunny have no information concerning this company’s use of animal testing.

Understanding Skin Deep® ratings: Every product and ingredient in Skin Deep® gets a two-part score – one for hazard and one for data availability.

Hazard Score

The Skin Deep ingredient hazard score, from 1 to 10, reflects known and suspected hazards linked to the ingredients.

A product’s hazard score is not an average of the ingredients’ hazard scores. It is calculated using a weight-of-evidence approach that factors in all of the hazards or health impacts associated with the ingredients. To see details of how our hazard scores are calculated, see the “Hazard Ratings” section of our [methodology](#).

Data Availability

The Skin Deep data availability rating reflects the number of scientific studies about the product or ingredient in the published scientific literature. Not all ingredients are equal when it comes to safety data. Some have been studied extensively. For others there is only a modest volume of research, and still others have not been assessed at all. The data availability rating indicates the scope of data on which EWG has based an ingredient and/or product score.

To calculate a product score, they review individual ingredient hazards and evaluate each product in relation to the rest of the products in the Skin Deep database. The safest products score well by both measures, with a low hazard rating and a fair or better data availability rating.

What does the EWG VERIFIED™ mark mean?

The EWG VERIFIED™ mark on a product indicates that the product meets EWG’s strictest standards for transparency and health.

✓ **Avoids EWG’s Ingredients of concern**

EWG VERIFIED products cannot contain any ingredients on EWG’s “Unacceptable” list, which includes ingredients with health, ecotoxicity and/or contamination concerns.

✓ **Full transparency**

EWG VERIFIED products must meet EWG’s standards for ingredient disclosure on the label; products with the VERIFIED mark are made by manufacturers that have been fully transparent with EWG about that product’s ingredients, including fragrance ingredients.

✓ **Good manufacturing practices**

EWG VERIFIED product manufacturers must develop and follow current good manufacturing practices to further ensure the safety of their products.

Overall perception and additional information

The Skin Deep database has been a valuable resource for consumers and advocates concerned about the safety of personal care products and cosmetics. The database is regularly updated and provides detailed information on ingredients and potential health hazards, as well as regulatory information. While there is no mobile app for Skin Deep, the database is easily accessible through the Environmental Working Group’s website and has received positive reviews and recognition for its contributions to consumer health and safety.

Yuka

Features

Yuka is a mobile app that provides users with information on the nutritional value and health impact of food and personal care products. The app uses a simple color-coded system to rate products based on their healthiness, and provides users with recommendations for healthier alternatives.

Functionalities

Yuka provides a range of functionalities to help users make healthier purchasing decisions. These include:

- **Scanning and product rating:** Users can scan the barcode of a food or personal care product to see its Yuka rating, which is based on the nutritional value and health impact of the product. The app uses a color-coded system to rate products as either green (healthy), orange (average), or red (unhealthy).
- **Product search:** Users can search for products to find information on their Yuka rating, ingredients, and nutritional value.
- **Personalized recommendations:** Based on a user's health goals and preferences, the app provides personalized recommendations for healthier food and personal care products.
- **Shopping list:** Users can create a shopping list of healthy products and receive alerts when these products go on sale.
- **Recipe suggestions:** The app provides users with recipe suggestions that are tailored to their health goals and preferences.

Revenue Model

Yuka generates revenue by offering premium features to users. For example, users can purchase a premium subscription that provides access to additional features, such as personalized advice and coaching, and discounts on healthy products. The company also generates revenue through partnerships with retailers and brands, who can pay to be featured on the app and website.

Ways to contribute: 3 different ways:

- **Version premium**

The paid version of the Yuka app allows users to subscribe to the Member version, which includes several additional features like a search bar, offline mode, and custom alerts that notify users of the presence of palm oil, gluten, or lactose. Yuka considers this premium version to be crucial in maintaining the project's independence. Individuals can decide on an annual plan that costs 10, 15, 20, or 50 Euros per year. If the Premium version fails to meet the user's expectations, they will receive a full refund, valid during the first 30 days of the subscription. Users can cancel their subscription anytime by accessing their account within the app.

- **Book Yuka**

"The Healthy Eating Guide" (available in France only). This 253-page book concentrates, in a simple and entertaining way, all the basics to turn to a healthy diet. 24.90€

- **Calendrier des fruits et légumes**

A calendar of seasonal fruits and vegetables (available in France only), made in France on paper derived from sustainably managed forests and packaged by individuals from a work reintegration program. 14.90€

Testing

In this case I scanned a hand product, specifically a hand soap. In addition to producing a rating, on a scale of 1 to 100, it gives the composition of the product divided by colour (red harmful, yellow medium harmful, green not harmful), and clicking on the component gives the description. It also shows similar and better alternatives in terms of the rating of the searched product. However, it does not produce information on the positive or negative impact on the environment.

The app only allows searching by barcode, and to search with text search box you need to subscribe to Premium.

The collage displays five screenshots from a mobile application:

- Top Left:** Product page for 'Jabón de manos DERMO Mildeen'. It shows a 7/100 rating (Malo) and a list of ingredients with their risk levels: Methylchloroisothiazolinone (De riesgo), Methylisothiazolinone (De riesgo), Sodium Laureth sulfate (Riesgo bajo), Cocamide DEA (Riesgo bajo), Cocamidopropyl betaine (Riesgo bajo), Tetrasodium EDTA (Riesgo bajo), Hexyl cinnamal (Riesgo bajo), and 8 other ingredients (Sin riesgo).
- Top Right:** Detailed view of 'Methylchloroisothiazolinone', categorized as 'De riesgo' and 'Alérgeno'. It includes a 'Detalles' section explaining its use as a preservative and a 'Fuentes científicas' section with a link to a CSSC document.
- Middle Left:** Continuation of the ingredient list from the first screenshot, showing 'Recarga Jabón de manos dermoprotector Deliplus' with a 72/100 rating.
- Middle Right:** A 'Mi alimentación' (My nutrition) screen featuring a carrot character and a bar chart, with a 'SÍNTESIS' section for scanning products.
- Bottom Right:** A 'Mis cosméticos' (My cosmetics) screen for the period '08 marzo → 08 abril', showing a summary of product quality scores.

Summary of Product Quality Scores (from bottom right screenshot):

Calificación	Cantidad
Excelente	0
Bueno	0
Mediocre	0
Malo	1

Options (from middle left screenshot):

- Añadir a favoritos
- Método de calificación
- ¿Algún problema con este producto?

In addition, I also scanned another product, body cream, scanned with other competitors, to see whether or not there was discrepancy in product rating. In this case Yuka produces a 23/100 for Deliplus Argan Cream, while for the simulation conducted with INCI Beauty had produced 7.4/20, so in line, i.e., not a very healthy product.

Overall perceptions and additional information

Overall, Yuka's revenue model and functionalities align with their mission of promoting healthy and informed consumer behaviour. The app is designed to empower users to make more informed and healthier purchasing decisions and support companies that prioritize healthy and sustainable practices.

In my opinion, Yuka is a good application that lets you know if it is a product is healthy or not, it does not provide exhaustive information for our research, but for a user who is at the supermarket and wants to know if the shampoo he is buying is harmful or not for his well-being can be helpful. Important point is that, in the description of the components/ingredients of the product, in addition to providing the characteristics it also provides a part where it says whether the substance is polluting or not and whether it can be harmful to the environment and other organisms. This is an app that applies (they say) the principles of transparency and non-influence, so it conveys a sense of trust in their assessment to the average consumer. Also, by paying and subscribing you can have many more features.

INCI Beauty Features

INCI Beauty is a French online platform that provides information and ratings on the safety and potential health hazards of personal care products and cosmetics. The platform analyzes the ingredients

in products and provides a score and detailed information on the safety and potential health hazards of each ingredient.

Functionalities

- Scan a product and search for personal care products and cosmetics by name, brand, or product type
- View scores and information on the safety and potential health hazards of products and their ingredients
- View detailed information on the ingredients in products, including their uses, functions, and potential health hazards
- Create a personal profile to save favourite products and searches
- Access articles and resources on personal care product safety and health
- Possibility of advertising in the application (brand, distributor, professional and laboratory)

Revenue Model

The INCI Beauty application was created by a French company totally independent financially.

INCI Beauty generates revenue through:

- INCI Beauty offers its users a Premium package at 14.99 Euros/year which gives access to extended functionalities
- Donations
- The INCI Beauty shop: The INCI Beauty merchandise shop offers T-shirts, Tote-bags and water bottles in the application's colours for sale
- INCI Beauty has developed a subscription system dedicated to professionals:
Brands can access statistics about their product, they can publish photos on a white background or respond to comments as a brand.
Distributors can access an API, which allows them to retrieve information on product compositions (Notes, INCI list, etc.).

Laboratories can access a score prediction system that allows them to evaluate the score of a product when it is not yet on the market and does not yet have a barcode

Testing

The INCI Beauty platform is available online and can be accessed through its website. Users can search for products, view scores and information on the safety and potential health hazards of products and their ingredients, and create a personal profile to save information and searches.

It is possible to search the list of ingredients to get an in-depth analysis, including which products contain these ingredients and what level of danger they have.

INCI Beauty INGREDIENTS SEARCH OPEN ACCESS PROS ENGLISH

Ingredients used in cosmetics

The INCI list (International Nomenclature of Cosmetic Ingredients) is a mandatory nomenclature on cosmetics since 1999. Created in 1973 by an American association, the INCI list (or list of ingredients) aims to standardize the ingredients present in a product cosmetic.

Nevertheless, the manufacturer is not obliged to indicate the concentration for each one of them because of "the secret of manufacture". However, we know that they are classified "compulsorily" in order of inverse concentration (from high to low) for those dosed at more than 1%. Below 1%, the manufacturer can make it appear in the order he wants on the box.

0-9 A B C D E F G H I J

K L M N O P Q R S T U V

W X Y Z

INCI Beauty INGREDIENTS SEARCH OPEN ACCESS PROS EN

DIMETHICONE

CAS number: 63148-62-9 / 9006-65-9 / 9016-00-6

✿ "Medium penalty" in all categories.

Origin(s): Synthetic
Other languages: Dimethicon, Dimeticona, Dimeticone, Diméthicone ou Polydiméthylsiloxane
INCI name: DIMETHICONE
EINECS/ELINCS number: - / - / - /
Comedogenic potential (pc): 1
Food additive: E900
Classification: Silicone

NAMELY

Dimethicone also called PDMS is a silicone that is not subject to any European restrictions. It is also the most used silicone in cosmetics. Its role is to produce a film of surface around the hair and on the skin, to protect them then (occlusive effect, with what that can imply). It also brings sweetness to the products and makes it easy to use creams and shampoos. It is a little "the Swiss knife of the chemist": it is used a little in all sauces, to make the products brighter, more pleasant and therefore more sellers, or to compensate for the drying effect of certain ingredients like surfactants.

This inert component poses no problem for human health, one can only wonder if its effect is not only marketing and artificial. It is on the ecological aspect that the ingredient can have a very negative impact since it is very little biodegradable.

Its functions (INCI)

- *Antifoaming* : Removes foam during manufacturing / reduces foam formation in liquid finished products
- *Emollient* : Softens and smoothes the skin
- *Skin conditioning* : Maintains skin in good condition
- *Skin protecting* : Helps to avoid the harmful effects of external factors on the skin

This ingredient is present in 16.63% of cosmetics.

Make-up palette (67.85%)
Cc cream (65.87%)
Foundation (63.54%)
Anti-aging box (59.84%)
Anti-ageing / anti-brown spot hand cream (57.02%)

Products that contain them

Schwarzkopf
Gliss Colour Perfector Après-shampooing
Protecteur pour Cheveux Colorés - 370 ml
0,4 / 20

Wella
Shampooing pour cheveux épais INVIGO
Color Brilliance 250 ml
0 / 20

In this case, the simulation was conducted with the brand 'Kjaer Weis', from the category 'Cosmetics'. One can search the search bar for the brand or product and INCI provides products with features such as the list of ingredients, their score and alternative products. They have also just released a new tool that automatically displays the INCI Beauty rating of a cosmetic product on any website.

INCI Beauty INGREDIENTS SEARCH OPE

Kjaer weis
(10 results)

Kjaer Weis

You may be looking for the brand [Kjaer weis](#)

Products

	Kjaer weis Fard à joues crème Embrace, Nude Rosé Subtil et Universel 18,8 / 20		
	Kjaer weis Poudre pressée 18,5 / 20		
	Kjaer weis Crème de teint Paper Thin 18,5 / 20		

INCI Beauty INGREDIENTS SEARCH OPEN ACCESS PROS ENGLIS

Fard à joues crème Embrace, Nude Rosé Subtil et Universel

3	Do you want to display this score on your site? 18.8/20	
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By rosee. 01/07/2019
Origin of the photo: France

Composition

AMMONIUM GLYCYRRHIZATE, ***** , CAPRYLIC/CAPRIC TRIGLYCERIDE, CERA ALBA (BEES WAX)*, CI 75470 (CARMINE), ***** , CI 77891 (TITANIUM DIOXIDE), COPERNICA CERIFERA (CARNAUBA) WAX*, ***** , GALLIC ACID, GARDENIA FLORIDA FRUIT EXTRACT, GLYCERYL STEARATE, ***** , MALTODEXTRIN, MICA, POLYGLYCERYL-3 DIISOSTEARATE, PRUNUS AMYGDALUS DULCIS (SWEET ALMOND) OIL*, RICINUS COMMUNIS (CASTOR) SEED OIL*, ROSA RUBIGINOSA (ROSE HIP) SEED OIL*, SIMMONDSIA CHINENSIS (JOJOBA) SEED OIL*, ***** , VANILLA PLANIFOLIA FRUIT EXTRACT*, ZEA MAYS (CORN) STARCH* (*) .

(*) Ingredients are displayed in alphabetical order and some have been deliberately hidden (*****), to get the exact composition, please use our applications.

Alternative products

	Benecos Compact Blush Mallow Rose (vegan) (5,50 g) 18,9 / 20		
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Below is the simulation using the application (via Android device).

The app allows you to change language and country of origin and there is a part where they explain how it works (also with explanatory videos on YouTube) and what their methodology is. To scan the product without the barcode, you have to be a premium customer. Here are the additional features of the premium plan, for 14.99€ per year. When scanning a product, you can also choose the 'mini product description' option.

Below is the part of the simulation using the barcode scanner.

I tested, first of all, 3 products, one hair product, one body cream and one cosmetic. All three were found and provided a lot of information, including: product description, their score (from 1 to 20), complete list of ingredients (with a detailed explanation of each one and subdivided by colour indicating the level of danger), alternatives to the scanned product, user comments and their ratings, the 'where to buy' with prices, certifications awarded (e.g. 'Green Dot' or 'Allergen free'), possibility of adding photos and editing the description (only with premium plan).

Important point is that, in the description of the components/ingredients of the product, in addition to providing the characteristics it also provides a part where it says whether the substance is polluting or not and whether it can be harmful to the environment and other organisms.

9:43

← CETEARYL ETHYLHEXANOATE

CAS number
90411-68-0

Functions (INCI)

- Emollient : Softens and smoothes the skin
- Hair conditioning : Leaves hair easy to comb, soft, soft and shiny and / or confers volume, lightness and shine
- Skin conditioning : Maintains skin in good condition

Present in 0.86 % of cosmetics. Main categories :

- Illuminators and complexion illuminator (6.89 %)
- Blush (6.02 %)
- Eyeshadow (4.74 %)
- Bronze powder / Sun powder (4.68 %)
- Compact powder (3.31 %)

8480000467669 Share

Deliplus Cream Com Oil de Argan - 250 ml

7.4/20

Composition

Medium penalty 8

Low penalty 5

No penalty 14

Complete list of ingredients:

- AQUA Water
- GLYCERIN Glycerin / E422
- CETEARYL ETHYLHEXANOATE
- PARAFFINUM LIQUIDUM Paraffin oil | Mineral oil
- GLYCERYL STEARATE Glyceryl stearate | Anionic surfactant

9:44

← 8480000467669 ☆

Deliplus Cream Com Oil de Argan - 250 ml

7.4/20

Alternatives

Cien Nature Organic Sea Buckthorn Body Lotion - 250 ml

15.6/20

Cien Nature Aloe Vera Bio Crema Corpo

18.7/20

Cottage Lait corps à l'huile d'Argan

15.7/20

Le Petit Marseillais Nutrition - Lait hydratant Beurre de Karité, Amande Douce & Huile d'Argan - 250 ml

12/20

L'Arbre Vert Lait Corps Réparateur à l'Huile d'Argan et Fleur d'Oranger - 250 ml

18.6/20

9:44

← 8480000467669 ☆

deliplus

Cream Com Oil de Argan - 250 ml

Volume

250 ml / 8.45 fl. oz (US)

PAO

12 month

Period after opening: this is the period during which you can use the product once it has been opened.

Natural extract

- Argan
- Shea
- Soy

Product category

Body milk and cream

9:44

← 8480000467669 ☆

Deliplus Cream Com Oil de Argan - 250 ml

7.4/20

Composition

Medium penalty 8

Only Premium members can use this feature. Login to our Open interface from a web browser to learn more.

BECOME A PREMIUM MEMBER OK

- AQUA Water
- GLYCERIN Glycerin / E422
- CETEARYL ETHYLHEXANOATE
- PARAFFINUM LIQUIDUM Paraffin oil | Mineral oil
- GLYCERYL STEARATE Glyceryl stearate | Anionic surfactant

The screenshot displays a mobile application interface. On the left, there are two photo thumbnails: the top one is dated 'January 24, 2023' and shows a jar of 'ARGAN delplus' cream; the bottom one is dated 'December 21, 2019' and shows the same product. On the right, a detailed view of a Maybelline 'Lasting Fix - Poudre Libre' product is shown, including its price '14.9/20' and social media engagement icons. Below the product image is a 'Composition' section with a list of ingredients and their regulatory status:

- TALC**: Talc / E553b | **Regulated**
- SILICA**: Silica
- DIMETHICONE**: Dimethicone / E900 | **Silicone**

Underneath, a 'May contain:' section lists:

- CI 77491**: Red dye (Iron trioxide) / E172 | **Regulated**, **Mineral dye**

At the bottom of the right panel, there are icons for camera, document, information (circled in red), star, and share.

Created in 1966, the Leaping Bunny label of the Coalition for Consumer Information on Cosmetics (USA, Canada) certifies that the company does not carry out tests on animals at all stages of the creation of its products.

Please note that Leaping Bunny does not certify that the product is vegan.

It is possible also to search for a product via text box search, or via a predefined list of product categories. In this case, I searched for 'Aveda', one of the products in my analysis which is part of the 'Shampoo' category. Again, the app provides products in their database from the Aveda brand.

I also did a simulation with the same product used as a test in competitor EWG's Healthy Living app ('CeraVe Hydrating Facial Cleanser'), as you can see both provide similar results, especially on the hazardousness of the ingredients. From an initial evaluation between the two competitors, the INCI Beauty app seems more comprehensive and interactive, as well as providing much more information.

Overall perception and additional information

INCI Beauty is the only application on the market that directly confronts its users, through its integrated discussion network, which is open to all comments. Thanks to this network, anyone can react and the slightest deviation from consistency, integrity or transparency on the part of INCI Beauty would be immediately sanctioned. The platform provides detailed information on ingredients and potential health hazards, as well as a score that indicates the overall safety of a product. While there is no mobile app for INCI Beauty, the platform is easily accessible through its website and has received positive reviews and recognition for its contributions to consumer health and safety.

In my opinion, both the web page and the application are very well done, so far one of the best for the use inherent in the CA study we are doing. It is user-friendly, interactive, engaging, and provides all the information a user needs. A strong point is certainly the presence of certifications that give a broader view of the product's sustainability and eco-friendly concept (Until now one of the only ones to provide them).

Honestly, one could do without the additional features of the premium plan, but the one that stands out from the other competitors is the Offline functionality, i.e. using the app even when not connected

to the internet. On a small note, I was sometimes annoyed by the advertising banners, but they are not massively present (by subscribing to the premium plan, advertising can be removed)

Greenity – Bio INCI Cosmetics

Features

Greenity is an Italian mobile application that allows users to learn about the ingredients in cosmetic products and identify more eco-friendly substances through an intuitive color-coding system. The app provides access to a vast and constantly expanding database containing thousands of cosmetic products, enabling users to make more informed and sustainable choices. The first app on the INCI (International Nomenclature of Cosmetic Ingredients) of cosmetics

Functionalities

- Search for the cosmetics you use and discover their ingredients
- Many filters to find the right product for you
- Exclude from your search ingredients you are allergic to
- Take advantage of the barcode You can even search for the product using your phone's camera.
- Constantly updated product database

Revenue Model

I could not find enough information on the revenue model, but apparently the applications are free.

Testing

There is the app for android and apple but no trace of a web page (via Android device).

Initially, as you can see in the following holes, before entering the Home page, you are asked 6 questions to understand your profile and make the app more helpful, including hair type, age range and what kind of skin my face has.

By searching for a product via the text search bar, you can browse the app's predefined category divided into: face, body, hair, makeup, children, men. And then enter the specifics, i.e. whether we are looking for a cream or rather an oil.

It is also possible to use a search filter, as, in this simulation, we selected shampoo and can filter by solid shampoo, dry shampoo, or by skin type or by including/excluding certain ingredients in the search.

Here, by searching for 'Aveda', analysing their product Dry Hair Oil, the app provides a simplified overview with only the product photo, the recommended price, the reviews given by users and their comments, and the list of ingredients divided by colour according to their level of hazard. Clicking on an ingredient describes what type it is (emulsifier in this case) and what kind of compatibility it has with the skin and the environment (in this case it says generally good).

There, it is also possible to search according to INCI and substances. As regards searching by barcode, I was not able to do any simulations as all the products I had available were not in their database.

Overall perceptions and additional information

4.5 Apple Store, 100.000+ on Google Play Store.

Based on user reviews, the app seems to be easy to use and helpful in making informed choices about eco-friendly cosmetics. Some users have commented that the app can be slow to load or may not have information on all products, but overall, the reviews are positive.

One of the obvious limitations is that the application is only in Italian. Outside of this, the app is designed in a simple but skilfully executed manner. Thanks to the integration of the INCI, the app is able to provide detailed information on the ingredients of cosmetics, personal beauty, etc. products. It provides fairly basic and simple information, but well-presented and with a few easy-to-understand words (especially the ingredients part). The weaknesses in my opinion are: the app does not give an overall assessment of the product and therefore there are only user ratings, there is advertising but little, it does not give any information on product certifications, little quantity of products in the database.

Annex 2: App Mock-Ups

- **Design 1:**
 - Big and easy-to-use navigation buttons at main page.
 - Vertical information distribution
 - Filters with all information displayed
 - User can get badges for the label scans.
 - The ability to find near shops and post new products
 - Learn section with a flat vertical distribution

Figure 16 - Main page (Left) | Explore Section (Right)

Figure 17 - Filter (Left) | Label Info (Right)

Figure 18 - Scanning (Left) | Labels detected (Right)

Figure 19 - Engage Section (Left) | Product view (Right)

Figure 20 - Nearby locations for a specific product

Figure 21 – Shop overview (Left) | Add Product (Right)

- **Design 3:**
 - This design is oriented to be used in-shop, that means users won't be able to download the app on their own.
 - Big and easy-to-use navigation buttons at main page.
 - Profile and Learn sections are no longer necessary therefore discarded.
 - Dropdown filters.
 - Vertical information distribution separated in categories.
 - Each store can publish their offers and products.

Figure 22 - Design 3 - Main page (Left) | Labels (Right)

Figure 23 - Design 3 - Filters (Left) | Labels Info (Right)

Figure 24 - Design 3 - Shop products (Left) | Product Description (Right)

Figure 25 - Design 3 - Shop Description with vouchers

Annex 3: Designed badges

3CO colour codes and format templates

3CO_Cover_8 pt
3CO_Cover_category 10 pt
3CO_Cover_Subtitle
3CO_Cover_Subtitle_2
3CO_Deliverable reference number
3CO_Head Executive Summary,Annex
3CO_Header contents
3CO_Lead beneficiary
3CO_Project funding no
3CO_standard
3CO_table content
3CO_table head
3CO_Title1
Standard
1 Überschrift 1,3CO_Header
1.1 Überschrift 2,3CO Header 2
1.1.1 Überschrift 3,3CO_Header 3
Fett,3CO_bold_blue
Beschriftung,3CO_labeling
Verzeichnis 1,3CO_List of contents
Verzeichnis 2,3CO_List of contents 2
Verzeichnis 3,3CO_List of contents 3
Abbildungsverzeichnis,3CO_List of figures
Fußzeile,3CO_footer
Kopfzeile,3CO_header

Figure 26: Important format templates

Colours

